

OP-06

**HOPE IN THE SHADOWS:
RESTORING WELL-BEING IN A
BEDBOUND PATIENT THROUGH
COMMUNITY NURSING IN AN
UNDERSERVED SETTING**

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“Hope never abandons you,
you abandon it.”

George Weinberg
American Psychologist

Background

- Delivering healthcare to marginalised communities poses significant challenges and is often suboptimal.
- Among the many unmet needs, psychosocial well-being is frequently overlooked, despite being integral to holistic health — particularly in underserved populations.

Case Description

- Mr. AB, a 41-year-old unmarried man, has been bedbound since 2022 following a train accident that resulted in paraplegia and significant upper body weakness.
- He resides in an urban informal settlement and is cared for by his sister, his primary caregiver.
- He is a known hypertensive patient registered for follow-up at the nearest Primary Medical Care Unit.

Case Description

- His repeated absence from clinic visits, despite his sister routinely collecting medications, was noted by the attending medical officer.
- Further inquiry revealed the circumstances of his disability and current living conditions.
- With the leadership of the institutional head, a home-based care plan was initiated to be delivered via the Public Health Nursing Officer (PHNO), supported by a healthcare assistant familiar with the locality.

21-11-2023

MO OPP

Door doctor 12

phosa kidney arrange catua

Ramand for the post off

Thank you

MO

21-17-2023

Loschan 25mg bd

Ulan @ 1000 IDU day 2/11

RVP 2/12

16/02/2024
16/10/91
over discharge

16/1

PMS.

Body aches.

Mx:

Losartan 25mg bd - 2/12

Referred to M/Clinic at LH

R/V NTC

SOS

Case Description

- The care plan included bi-monthly visits for blood pressure monitoring, physiotherapy, and blood sampling for investigations.
- Initially, the patient showed features of depression, confined to bed with limited interaction.
- However, through regular visits, trust and therapeutic rapport was developed.
- Over time, he regained upper body strength and can now sit upright. His mood has also improved; he is more engaged with care and expresses renewed optimism about life.

Conclusion

- This case highlights how simple yet impactful measures by a primary healthcare team can significantly uplift the quality of life of a bedbound patient.
- It underscores the importance of addressing psychosocial well-being, which not only enhances a patient's acceptance of care but also helps build trust in the healthcare system among underserved communities.

Acknowledgements

- Other staff members at PMCU Sedawatte who facilitate the home visits of the patient
- The community members around PMCU Sedawatte

**“Alone we can do s o little,
together we can do so much”**

Helen Keller

American author, disability rights advocate

political activist and lecturer

THANK YOU